

Title: Getting Buy-In: How to Plan Inclusive Open Access Sessions

Instructors:

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Description:

Advocacy is a core element of scholarly communication (SC) work, particularly when it comes to promoting open scholarship and new modes of communication. SC officers must know their audience and strike the right balance between educating their community and advocating for transformations the community may not be ready to embrace. A fundamental understanding of matters related to advocacy, negotiation, diversity, accessibility, equity, and inclusion is essential both to reach varied audiences and to encourage richer, more open and more accessible resources.

This course presents strategies for developing effective SC-related communications ranging from “elevator” pitches to full-length workshops. We implement a variety of pedagogical methods, including lectures, active participation through in-class discussion and live polls, and group and individual exercises. Students are invited to bring examples of real-life scenarios to try with communication strategies covered in class. The class includes dynamic exercises and discourse, and a guest scholar, and encourages active participation based around the development of soft skills. This course presents strategic solutions to problem-solving, including relevant programs, tools, and technologies.

Part 1: Advocacy-based Meetings, Conversations, and Project Work

The course begins with an introduction to strategic thinking in communication, the foundation for all forms of scholarly communications outreach and advocacy. We cover the different types of crucial outreach activities and how to apply strategic thinking to these modalities, and discuss how advocacy work is contextual. Class conversation includes topics related to equity, diversity, and inclusion, implicit bias, privilege, accessibility, and negotiation. Exercises and discussion will include concepts of understanding how cultural constructs impact advocacy, relationships, behavioral change, privilege, and buy-in.

Part 2: Advocacy-based, Inclusion-Focused Events, and Technical Labor

This part of the course builds upon Part 1 by introducing students to more in-depth techniques to strategically customize communications and advocacy-driven messages, and to include deliberate methods in presentations and public communications. Additional considerations for facilitating events with audiences of various sizes will be covered, as well as tips for building and tracking campus champions and partners, use of technology platforms, and rights and legal

frameworks and considerations for use in advocacy or inclusion work. During this session, discussion and exercises will include strategic solutions focused on technologies, tools, and platforms that help scaffold advocacy-based initiatives.

Level: Beginner to intermediate

Intended audience: The course is intended for individuals who are new to working in scholarly communication and open access or who are already engaged in the work and are looking to increase their skills in advocacy, education, and stakeholder outreach. Librarians, early-career researchers, administrators, publishers, and graduate students are encouraged to register. This course is also intended for anyone looking to increase their cultural awareness competencies and perspectives on inclusion, diversity, and negotiation.

Requirements: This course requires a minimal amount of optional advance preparation, which involves students being asked to think about their home institutions and bring with them examples of scenarios relevant to their work. Shared discussion and activities will occur, respecting confidentiality and consent. A basic understanding of scholarly communication and open access is recommended. Optional, non-required opportunities will be provided to class participants who are interested before and during FSCI2020 (such as pre- and post-class surveys, and optional suggested readings).

Course Learning Objectives

A participant in this course will, at the end of the course, be able to:

- Name common stakeholder groups within campus, institution, and organization structures, and communication styles to use with each group.
- Gain awareness of matters relating to equity, diversity, and inclusion that affect negotiation and communication.
- Describe common factors and considerations for successful communications, advocacy-based events, and presentations, and identity tools to help manage these sessions.
- Use tools from the course in the application of future programming, instruction, workshops, and sessions.
- Identify elements of strategic thinking, negotiation, rights management, and technology as applied to advocacy based and inclusion focused outreach, and how to employ methods for successful outcomes.

Course Topics

This course will cover these topics over 4 sessions:

- Advocacy
- Communication
- Diversity
- Inclusion

- Buy-in

Course Schedule

LIVE ZOOM SESSION SCHEDULE

(All times Pacific)

Wednesday, Aug. 5

8-10AM: Session 1

5-7PM: REPEAT Session 1

Monday, Aug. 10

8-10AM: Session 2

12-1:30PM: Session 3, guest Peter Suber – Writing, reading, speaking: an interactive discussion on advocacy

Wednesday, Aug. 12

8-10AM: Session 4

Sessions may include at least one hands-on exercise, discussions, and lectures.

Session 1 (not recorded but repeated)

- Instructor and class introductions
- Defining advocacy around structures and roles
- Planning and preparing for consultations and group presentations
- Wrap Up: Q&A and activities

Session 2 (recorded)

- Diversity, equity, and inclusion matters
- Accessibility and disability matters
- Effective, inclusive, and culturally aware communications
- Rights management and licensing
- Wrap Up: Q&A and activities

Session 3 (not recorded)

- Writing, reading, speaking: an interactive discussion on advocacy: guest speaker (Peter Suber, synchronous)

Session 4 (recorded)

- Using communication, negotiation, and leadership skills at the advocacy table
- Building and preparing for scholarly communication classes, events, and workshops
- Identifying and collaborating with institutional OA champions and other partners
- Why This Matters: Getting Inclusive Buy In
- Wrap-up: New skills, and resources for continued learning

Course Materials and Supplies Required

Participants may be expected to complete a minimal amount of the prerequisite work before the course, such as example research activities below.

Recommended Readings: There will be a couple short readings for registered participants to skim and review briefly prior to class. See section below.

Research Activities:

Prior to the first session, participants can choose to retrieve copies of the following information, if applicable, about their institutions to help inform discussion.

- Library/workplace and broader organizational charts
- Institutional strategic mission and values
- Academic or governance structure
- University or institutional open access policy, resolution, or mandate, if applicable to your home institution

Recommended Readings

Bell, L. Hearing all our Voices: Applications of Feminist Pedagogy to Conferences, Speeches, and Panel Presentations. 1993. *Women's Studies Quarterly* 21(3/4): 107-113.

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/40022012>

Malenfant, K. Open and Equitable Scholarly Communications: Creating a More Inclusive Future. *ACRL Insider*, June 12, 2019. <https://www.acrl.ala.org/acrlinsider/archives/17807>.

Parsons, J. Open Access: Advocacy (interview with Peter Suber). *Library Journal*, March 29, 2017. <https://www.libraryjournal.com/?detailStory=open-access-advocacy>

Patterson, K, Grenny, J, McMillan, R, Switzler, A. Excerpts from “What’s a Crucial Conversation” and “Learn to Look”, in *Crucial Conversations: Tools for Talking when Stakes are High*, 2nd edition. New York: McGraw Hill Professional, 2011.

Schapiro, D. “Is Identity Negotiable?”, in *Negotiating the Nonnegotiable: How to Resolve Your Most Emotionally Charged Conflicts*. New York: Penguin Books, 2017.

Supplemental readings that will be referenced in the course and for further reading after FSCI will follow in the next section and in the Open Science Framework class portal. Students registered for this class will receive information on accessing the portal.

Supplemental Resources & Readings

Advocacy

Coalition of OA Policy Institutions (COAPI) Public COAPI Toolkit of Open Access Policy Resources: <https://osf.io/vhw6d/>

Davis-Kahl, S. Engaging undergraduates in scholarly communication: Outreach, education, and advocacy. *College and Research Library News*. 2012; 73(4): 212-222. <https://crln.acrl.org/index.php/crlnews/article/view/8744>

Harvard Open Access Project. Good Practices for University Open Access Policies. <https://bit.ly/goodoa>.

Open Access Directory, http://oad.simmons.edu/oadwiki/Main_Page

Piwowar, H, Priem, J, Lariviere, V, Alperin, JP, Matthias, L, Norlander, B, Farley, A, West, J, Haustein, S. The state of OA: a large-scale analysis of the prevalence and impact of Open Access articles. *PeerJ*. 2018; 6:e4375. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.4375>

Scholarly Publishing & Academic Resources Coalition (SPARC). Open Access Advocacy: A Checklist for Research Libraries. 2009. <http://sparc.arl.org/resource/open-access-advocacy-checklist-research-libraries>

Understanding Stakeholder Beliefs & Values

Cantrell, M, Collister, L. The status quo bias and the uptake of open access. *first monday* 2019; 24(7). <https://firstmonday.org/ojs/index.php/fm/article/view/10089>

Blankstein, M., Wolff-Eisenberg, C. Ithaka S&R US Faculty Survey 2018. <https://sr.ithaka.org/publications/2018-us-faculty-survey/>

University of California Libraries. Author Focus Groups and Surveys, and Publisher Survey. Pay it Forward: Investigating a Sustainable Model of Open Access Article Processing Charges for Large North American Research Institutions. 2016: pp 19-36. https://www.library.ucdavis.edu/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/ICIS-UC-Pay-It-Forward-Final-Report.rev_7.18.16.pdf

Critical Pedagogy & Instructional Design

ACRL Instruction Section Research & Scholarship Committee. Five Things You Should Read About Critical Librarianship. 2017. https://acrl.ala.org/IS/wp-content/uploads/20170602_research_5Things.pdf

Alexander, L, Colman, J, Kahn, M, Peters A, Watkinson, C, Welzenbach, R. Publishing as Pedagogy: Connecting Library Services and Pedagogy. *Educause Review*. January 11, 2016. <https://er.educause.edu/articles/2016/1/publishing-as-pedagogy-connecting-library-services->

[and-technology](#)

Pastore, R. Performing a Task Analysis in Instructional Design. 2015.

<http://raypastore.com/wordpress/2015/03/2747/>

Tewell, E. Putting Critical Information Literacy into Context: How and Why Librarians Adopt Critical Practices in their Teaching. *In the Library with the Lead Pipe*. 2016.

<http://www.inthelibrarywiththeleadpipe.org/2016/putting-critical-information-literacy-into-context-how-and-why-librarians-adopt-critical-practices-in-their-teaching/>

Diversity, Equity & Inclusion

Association of College & Research Libraries. Open and Equitable Scholarly Communications: Creating a More Inclusive Future. 2019.

<http://www.ala.org/acrl/sites/ala.org.acrl/files/content/publications/booksanddigitalresources/digital/resec.pdf>

Coalition for Diversity & Inclusion in Scholarly Communications. Joint Statement of Principles.

<https://c4disc.org/principles/>

Culley, T. What a new Publons Report on Peer Review Says About Diversity, and More. *Scholarly Kitchen*. September 18, 2018. <https://scholarlykitchen.sspnet.org/2018/09/12/guest-post-what-a-new-publons-report-on-peer-review-says-about-diversity-and-more/>.

OpenCon. Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion - a conference planning report.

<https://sparcopen.github.io/opencon-dei-report/>.

Tavernier, WL. Scholarly Communications, Equity, and Inclusion. University of Indiana Libraries.

2018. <https://blogs.libraries.indiana.edu/scholcomm/2018/10/23/scholarly-communications-diversity-and-the-academy/>

Other Helpful Information

- Course materials will be available in OSF.
- Students requiring or preferring ADA (American Disabilities Act) accommodations are welcome to contact the course instructors. Please submit requests for ADA accommodations should be requested as early as possible prior to class.
- You will learn the most from this course if you come prepared and interested in active engagement and course work. We look forward to meeting everyone!